

Achieving Educational Effectiveness Through Quality Teaching in Nigerian Secondary Schools

Dr. Carol O. Ezeugbor

Department of Educational Management and Policy
Faculty of Education
Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka.

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Abstract

Lack of quality teaching is one of the greatest problems staring at the face of the Nigerian educational system. This paper therefore examined the achievement of educational effectiveness through quality teaching in Nigerian Secondary Schools. It was a survey design carried out in Anambra State. The population was made up of 5902 and 3702 teachers from Public and Private Secondary Schools respectively. The study was guided by three research; questions and two null hypotheses tested at the 0.05 level of significance. A 21-item; questionnaire used to procure relevant information for the study was validated by experts with a reliability coefficient of $r = 0.80$. Mean and t -test statistics were used in data analysis. The study revealed that teachers' knowledge of the teaching content, their level of communication and teaching methodologies were factors that enhanced educational effectiveness in secondary schools. Based on the findings, recommendations were made.

Key words: *Effectiveness, Teaching, Secondary School, Quality*

Introduction

Secondary education is a very critical level in the Nigerian educational system, and it is the bedrock on which higher education is built in any society. In Nigeria, secondary schools provide academic programmes and general education for the students to be aware of socio-economic and political situation, technological development-personal problems and preparation needed for useful living within the society and achievement of higher education (NPE, 2004: 18). Therefore, the role of teachers is indispensable in this area: hence, teachers are resource agent to education. However, Dike (2005) opined that the quality of education in Nigeria has fallen since the past two decades and this could be traced from the inception of the military dictatorship in Nigeria in 19R4. The continued high rate of youth unemployment in the country, and the fact that students are inadequately equipped compared to their counterparts that are adequately trained in the West is a concern to all the stake holders of Nigerian educational system (Dike 200S).

Adeniyi, (2001) and Peretomode, (1991), argued that the fallen standards in Nigeria's educational system can also be traced to cultural, religious, social, technological and above all

economic reasons. However, Pillai, (2001) posited that what is wrong with secondary education cannot be blamed on teachers alone, yet there is no doubt that man's contemporary existence is dominated by teaching. There is also a universal recognition of the need to use professionally qualified teachers in instructional processes, as we enter the era of globalization where school effectiveness and quality improvement are the order of the day. There seems to have been some efforts on the part of the Federal, State government and other agencies such as nongovernmental organizations and the Education Trust Fund, in providing enough quality teachers for the take off of the Universal Basic Education in Nigeria through seminars, induction courses and on the job-training; hence quality assurance in education as regards human resources has formed the top agenda for discussion by all providers of education. Therefore the extent to which Nigerian education would succeed in achieving its set goals and objectives depends considerably on a dedicated, knowledgeable and inspired teaching force.

Nonetheless, quality in teaching means possessing the competencies; to teach effectively. The competencies required include the ability of the teacher to measure students' educational achievements and of ensuring that parents are satisfied with the educational development of their children and wards for which overall concern is the effective improvement of-children educational development. Essentially therefore, improving the quality of education will be improving student's learning achievement qualitatively, which is dependent on the qualitative improvement of teachers. A *difficult* aspect of quality oversight arises when problems are found in terms of educational effectiveness. Effectiveness is not one dimensional, but depends on the way various factors work in combination. Fundamentally, it requires a look at outcomes and what an institution accomplishes. It means questions about whether school graduates are well prepared, whether they have both the knowledge and skills that they and society expect as a result of their studies.

Chapman and Austin (2002) noted that "quality of education" often means raising the level of academic performance of students, usually as measured in test scores, in the various subjects, which form part of their school curriculum. In actual fact, teachers are a very, vital force in educational effectiveness at classroom instructional level. They are charged with the responsibility of implementing the school auricular, and the pedagogical techniques sufficiently, and showing effective instructional behaviours.

Given that learning is regarded as the central issue of the twenty-first century, the most painful, engaging, rewarding and enjoyable aspects of our personal and collective experiences need to be backed up with the services of highly qualified teachers (Pillai. 2001). A highly qualified teacher gets most students to use the higher cognitive level processes than the more academic students use spontaneously. Teaching works by getting students to engage in learning-related activity that helps them attain the particular objectives set for the unit or courses, such as theorizing, generating new ideas, reflecting, applying and problem-solving. However, Nigeria needs highly specialized teachers to aid teaching and learning and educational management for school effectiveness, hence, the study.

Statement of the Problem

Depending on the quality of teachers or the stock of available teaching capital the quantity and quality of educational output and its effectiveness will be greater or smaller. Apparently, the goals of secondary school education are to prepare students for useful living within the society and develop the totality of their minds. To achieve this, the federal government recommended a teacher-student ratio of 1:40 in secondary schools (FRN, 2004). In contrary, the researcher observed during her teaching practice supervision of students in June, 2008 at Onitsha, Nnewi and; Awka towns, that there were up to 50 students and more in a class especially at junior secondary sections. Some permanent teachers were observed teaching without instructional materials and lesson notes. There was evidence of insufficient class work and take home assignments/by the students.

Some private secondary schools employed teachers with low teaching qualifications (or none at all) perhaps to cope with the payment of salaries.

With this situation, it appears doubtful if public and private secondary schools actually maintain this quality teaching, hence the study was conceptualized: to investigate the achievement of educational effectiveness through quality teaching in Nigeria secondary schools.

Research Questions:

The following research questions guided the study:

1. How does teachers' knowledge of the teaching content enhance educational effectiveness?
2. To what extent does teachers' level of communication with students assist in achieving educational effectiveness?
3. How does teachers' method of teaching enhance educational effectiveness?

Hypotheses

The study tested the following null hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance.

1. Institutional type will not significantly influence the mean ratings of teachers' perception of quality teaching for educational effectiveness.
2. There is no significant difference between male and female teachers on the mean ratings of their perception of quality teaching for educational effectiveness.

Table 1: Mean ratings of teachers responses on the knowledge of teaching content

Achieving educational effectiveness depends on:	Teachers of public school	Teachers of private school	Average mean	Decision
Teachers good knowledge of Subject matter	2.94	2.76	2.85	Agree
Widely knowledge in all subjects	2.42	2.45	2.44	Disagree
Teaching with passion and humour	2.39	2.35	3.37	Disagree
The involvement of students into the process of acquiring new knowledge	3.00	3.08	3.04	Agree

The development of critical thinking in the students	3.45	2.88	3.17	Agree
The ability of the teachers to stimulate students to learn	3.23	3.51	3.37	Agree
The effectiveness of time usage	3.33	3.00	3.11	Agree
Teacher connects the theoretical part of the subject with the real world of work	3.62	3.50	3.56	Agree
Teacher aims at all round development of students minds	2.73	2.81	2.77	Agree

From table 1, it is observed that seven items out of nine have mean scores well above the cut-off mean of 2.50, indicating the respondents' agreement that they are the knowledge of teaching contents necessary for achieving educational effectiveness. The other two items have mean scores below 2.50 and are therefore not the knowledge of teaching contents necessary for achieving educational effectiveness.

The decision from these mean ratings is that teachers' knowledge of the teaching content enhances the achievement or educational effectiveness in Nigerian secondary schools.

Table 2: Mean ratings of teachers' responses on their level or communication with students

Items	Teachers of public school	Teachers of private school	Plan	Decision
Achieving educational effectiveness depends on:	3.46	3.21	3.33	High
Interaction between teachers and students	3.61	3.50	3.56	High
Approachableness of teachers and students	3.55	3.52	3.59	High
Transparency in evaluating students	2.85	3.99	2.92	High
Clarity of facts in teaching				
Availability of teachers for students' consultations	2.56	2.84	2.7	High
Exchange of phone numbers and e-mail addresses with students	2.30	2.44	2.37	High

Results in table 2 show that six out of seven items have mean scores above the cut-off mean of 2.50, indicating the respondents' high perception of teachers' level of communication. The only item with mean score of 2.37 which is below the cut-off mean of 2.50 shows that the respondents

perceive that teachers' exchange of phone numbers and e-mail addresses is not a level of communication required for achieving educational effectiveness.

The decision from these mean ratings is that teachers' level of communication with students assists in achieving educational effectiveness in Nigerian secondary schools.

Table 3: Mean ratings of teachers responses on methodology of teaching

Items	Teachers of public school	Teachers of private school	Average mean	Decision
Achieving educational effectiveness depends on:	3.46	3.21	3.33	High
Teaching skill (theory, explanation, etc)	3.61	3.50	3.56	High
Effective class control	3.55	3.52	3.59	High
Appropriate use of teaching aids	2.85	3.99	2.92	High
Demonstration of teaching situation	2.56	2.84	2.7	High
Teacher-student ratio is adequate	2.30	2.44	2.37	High

Results in table 3 indicate that live out of six items have mean/score above 2.50, showing the respondents' agreement that they are the teaching methods that enhance the achievement of educational effectiveness. The only item with mean score of 2.35 which is below the decision level of 2.50 is not a teaching method for enhancing the achievement of educational effectiveness.

The decision from these mean ratings is that teachers' methods of teaching enhance the achievement of educational effectiveness in Nigerian secondary schools.

Table 4: The t-test summary of differences in perception of teachers about teaching quality and institutional type

School type	No. Of subjects	Mean rating	Standard deviation (SD)	t-calculated	t-critical
Public	312	2.00	0.72		
	259	2.14	0.79	0.06	1.96

$p > 0.05$, t -calculated = 0.06, $< t$ -critical of 1.96.

In table 4, the. calculated t -value or 0.06 is less than the t -critical or 1.96, thereby indicating the non-rejections of the null hypothesis. Therefore, no significant difference exists in the mean ratings of the teachers of public and private secondary schools on quality teaching for educational effectiveness.

Table 5: The t-test summary of differences in the mean ratings or the perception female teachers on teaching quality.

School type	Gender	Number	Mean	SD	df	t-calculated	t-calculated
Public	Female	200	2.0R	0.72	509	0.09	
	Male	112	1.74	0.52			1.96
Private	Female	145	2.00	0.61	569	0.07	
	Male	114	1.74	0.78			

Table 5 shows that at 0.05 level of significance the calculated t for teachers in public school is 0.09 while the t-calculated for teachers in private school is 0.07, 0.09 and 1.07 are less than the t-critical of 1.96 and therefore the null hypothesis is accepted. Thus, no significant difference exists in the mean ratings or the perception of male and female teachers on quality teaching for educational effectiveness.

Discussion

The findings in table 1 indicate that the teachers' knowledge or the teaching content enhances their achievement or educational effectiveness. This is in line with McCormick. (1996) who noted that the best teachers are captivated by their subject matter drawn out of themselves by their teaching, which will catch their excitement like the wake or a passing train. This is not surprising to the researcher because today, teachers are aware that for learning to take place, there must be a change in behaviour in the students. This change in behaviour involves the acquisition of new knowledge, development of critical thinking and all round development of the students. Little wonders why this study revealed teachers' sensitivity on the improvement of quality teaching for school effectiveness.

An overview of the findings in table 2 show that teachers' level of communication with students is high. Anderson, (2002) noted that effective and qualitative teaching centre on students' classroom behaviour, interactions, participation and teachers' positive relationships with students. This is important because the relationship between students and teachers is an aspect of education that neither teachers nor students can afford to ignore. Thus, the construction of a classroom relationship is a visible consequence of the structuring of classroom learning.

The failure of teachers to exchange mobile phone numbers and e-mail addresses is not surprising to the researcher. This is because O. Ezeugbor (2008) in her studies on ICT competence level of Nigeria tertiary institution teachers, observed that Nigerian teachers' ICT competence level is below satisfaction. Most teachers in the secondary schools have demonstrated a lack of understanding of the basic skills associated with computer proficiency, hence they have failed to exchange mobile phone numbers and e-mail addresses for students assignments and interactions. The findings in table 3, revealed that on the average, teachers perceive that adequate teaching methodology makes schooling more effective. Agreeing with this finding. Ololube, (2005) argued that it is the quantity of instruction that is improved by effectively applying the methodological principles that matter which particularly leads to improvement in students' outcomes. This holds water because for them students in secondary schools to learn qualitatively, the teacher must

demonstrate in his teaching a mastery of the teaching skills; delivering fluently, having effective class control, using adequate teaching aids to convey his message and also engaging the students in some extra curricular activities. Therefore teachers through instructional efficiency have been able to instruct the students to the extent that they attain academic excellence.

The findings also revealed that teacher-student ratio is inadequate. This gains the admiration of Olaseinde, (2006) when he noted that the teaching personnel in Nigerian secondary schools is not only inadequate when compared with the astronomical growth in the students' population, but also professionally unqualified. This situation negates the government policy of teacher-student ratio of 1:40 (FRN, 2004). The researcher's observation during the teaching practice supervision in 2008 where some classes in junior secondary schools in Onitsha, Nnewi and Awka towns have up to 50 students affirms this position. This would likely affect the delivery, engagement of students in critical thinking through class work and assignments and general interaction with the students.

This work has also indicated that institutional type and sex of teachers have no significant influence on the teaching quality (knowledge or teaching content, level of teachers' communication with students and teaching methods)' for' educational effectiveness. This finding is in agreement with McCormick in Ololube (2005) who argues that the extent of quality educational effectiveness through quality teaching are perceived to be the same by both teachers of public and private secondary schools. This is probably because they are all interested in achieving excellence through students' effective and excellent performances in schools.

Conclusion

The study investigated the effectiveness of the secondary school educational system through quality teaching. The study identified twenty-one teaching qualities, all or which but, four, were accepted as teachers' areas of quality in teaching for effective educational systems. Good knowledge of teaching content, effective communication with students and the use of adequate teaching methodologies are bedrock of educational effectiveness in Nigerian secondary schools.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

The inspectorate department of the Ministry of Education should ensure that public and private secondary schools are supervised more regularly to maintain the quality of teaching in the schools.

State Ministries of Education as the government arm should conduct on a regular bases, the retraining of teachers. Apart from its professional value, it saves considerable government expenditure, if it is done on the job.

Teachers should be compelled to acquire ICT training and utilize its gains in teaching: To implement the policy on teacher-student ratio (1:40), the government should employ more qualified teachers for teaching appointment in secondary schools.

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